

AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan II (D7.1)

Seascape Belgium

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1. List of referenced acronyms

AQUARIUS	Aqua Research Infrastructure Services for the health and protection of our unique, oceans, seas and freshwater ecosystems
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CDP	Communication & Dissemination Plan
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DTO	Digital Twin Ocean
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RI	Research Infrastructure
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SG	Stakeholder Group
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
TG	Target Group
TA	Transnational Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

2. Summary

This document constitutes the review and update (Version II) of the first version of the “AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination Plan” (Deliverable 7.1). It details the approach to and implementation of AQUARIUS communication and dissemination activities, providing a high-level overview of the first 18 months of activities and noting any necessary changes. A more detailed account of the outcomes of the AQUARIUS dissemination and communication actions will be provided in Deliverable D7.4 (M24).

The plan is designed to maximise the impact of AQUARIUS activities across all Work Packages, in particular, through raising awareness, mobilising engagement and promoting uptake of AQUARIUS results with target stakeholder groups. The approach to the plan considered the objectives (why), target stakeholder groups (who), key messages (what), timing and phases (when), tools and materials (how), main channels (where), together with key performance indicators.

While this Plan and activities in WP7 lead, coordinate, and support communication and dissemination across all work packages, all partners contribute to communication and dissemination. AQUARIUS has benefited from the engagement and commitment of all partners in this regard.

All updates in this document are highlighted in a green box preceded by “**Update C&D Plan Version II.**”. This is a living document that will be updated periodically by the WP7 team; it is now officially delivered as Version 2.0 to meet D7.1 (M18) of the project.

Figure 1. Snapshot of WP7 outputs during the first 18 months of AQUARIUS

3. Background and context to the AQUARIUS Communication & Dissemination Plan

3.1. The AQUARIUS concept

Research infrastructures are facilities, resources and services used by the research community to conduct research and promote innovation. They facilitate scientific research within national settings, across borders and in global collaborations.

Europe has a rich landscape of research infrastructures that enable marine and freshwater research and innovation. However, there is a critical need for greater integration of these research infrastructures to facilitate a more collaborative and holistic approach to research and innovation that contributes toward achieving healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems, in line with the objectives of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030. Addressing this need is the central aim of AQUARIUS: to integrate research infrastructures, enabling research and innovation that addresses challenges and explores opportunities for the sustainability of marine and freshwater ecosystems. The thematic and geographic scope of AQUARIUS is inspired by the Mission objectives and Lighthouse regions, respectively.

Figure 2. AQUARIUS geographic scope is informed by the Mission Ocean Lighthouse regions

The specific objectives of AQUARIUS are to:

1. Coordinate the enhancement and integration of a diverse range of top-level infrastructure services;
2. Provide efficient, single-point, transnational access to a broad range of integrated research infrastructures;
3. Design, develop, and manage Transnational Access Funding Calls to the research infrastructures;
4. Facilitate efficient and timely access to the distributed research infrastructure portfolio, for selected projects, according to the needs of the selected user communities;
5. Deliver highly effective training and scientific and technical support for users of the research infrastructures;
6. Ensure advanced data management, interoperability, as well as the connection of digital services (e.g., data services) to the European Open Science Cloud;

7. **Maximise the impact of AQUARIUS through dynamic dissemination, exploitation and communication activities, ensuring that the projects using the integrated research infrastructures can support the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters.**

3.2. Maximising impact

Effective dissemination, communication and exploitation activities are a contractual obligation of Horizon Europe funding. They play a crucial role in ensuring that the project delivers long-term impact and a return on the public investment. They raise the visibility of European research and innovation capacity and ensure that project results are widely shared and made accessible, particularly with target users, thus strengthening the European Research Area and creating a legacy for the project.

To maximise the impact of AQUARIUS, Work Package 7 designs, develops, implements and updates the project's Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy including by:

- Designing an impact-driven Communication and Dissemination Plan, for implementation throughout the project (Task 7.1);
- Promoting outreach and engagement of Transnational Access Funding Calls and ensuring broad dissemination of the project and its results (Task 7.2);
- Fostering and activating paths towards exploitation and uptake of results (Task 7.3); and
- Delivering strategic foresight and road-mapping to bridge the science-to-policy gap (Task 7.4), for impact and legacy.

This document details the second version of the AQUARIUS '**Communication & Dissemination Plan**' (CDP) (Deliverable 7.1). It includes the stakeholder engagement strategy, identifying the different target groups (who), the objectives of the CDP (why), key messages (what), timing and phases (when), tools and materials (how), and main channels (where). In addition, it details Key Performance Indicators (KPI) that will be used to monitor progress. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities in AQUARIUS can be considered at two levels:

1. *Level one* concerns the activities, results and outputs across the seven AQUARIUS work packages.
2. *Level two* concerns the selected Transnational Access (TA) Projects, their activities and results.

Update C&D Plan Version II. A separate 'Exploitation Plan Outline' (Deliverable D7.2) was developed at Month 12, which outlines the exploitation pathways to be developed for the project's key exploitable results (KER) during and beyond the project. A final Exploitation Plan will be delivered by Task 7.3 at the end of the project (Month 48). Task 7.3 will also work with the Transnational Access Projects to develop dedicated exploitation plans for their key exploitable results.

4. Why: Aim and objectives

The AQUARIUS Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy aims to maximise the impact of the project through well-designed and dynamic dissemination and communication activities. It has four main objectives:

1. To raise awareness of AQUARIUS, its activities and the value of this public investment amongst diverse stakeholders, including wider society;
2. To maximise engagement of target stakeholder groups throughout the project and beyond, by encouraging applications to the TA Funding Calls and provided training opportunities;

3. To maximise exploitation of AQUARIUS results and those of the selected projects towards generating long-term impact for the project;
4. To create an AQUARIUS legacy.

These objectives will be achieved by identifying our target stakeholders, developing tailored messages and calls to action and implementing a strategic approach to delivering these messages at the right time and using the appropriate channels. These aspects are detailed further below.

5. Who: Target groups & stakeholder engagement strategy

Five main Target Groups (TGs) have been identified for AQUARIUS communication and dissemination activities. These are further detailed below, explaining why they are important target groups.

TG#1 – Aquatic research scientists and academia and scientific networks and projects: To promote more collaborative and holistic marine and freshwater research contributing to healthy and sustainable ocean and waters by creating connections, building capacity amongst existing and next-generation researchers in the use of (new) integrated transnational access research infrastructure services, implementing FAIR¹ data management and effective use of virtual research environments for (big) data analytics.

TG#2 - Relevant EU and global Research Infrastructures (RIs), long-term EU and global data services and Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO): To explain the rationale behind AQUARIUS, co-design the portfolio of services, share best practices and promote the value of greater coordination and optimisation within the EU Research Infrastructure landscape and beyond. To anticipate exploitation pathways for the new data generated through enhanced transnational access opportunities through FAIR data management.

TG#3 - Industrial communities and SMEs: To promote opportunities for research scientists from industry to collaborate in TA Projects; to disseminate AQUARIUS outputs and results, promote exploitation and innovation; and, to build the Research Infrastructure community of stakeholders beyond the current project network and scope.

TG#4 - Policy platforms, decision-makers and funding bodies: To promote the work and value of AQUARIUS; to gather long-term support from policy-makers and funders for the sustainability of the research infrastructure services; and, to demonstrate the value of efforts towards further integration of services and future collaboration across European Research Infrastructures in support of EU and international policy goals.

TG#5 - Wider (non-expert) society including citizen science groups: To build awareness of the project with wider society explaining the importance of the European Research Infrastructure landscape and the added value of AQUARIUS for the European tax-payer. To promote the opportunities for citizen science groups to apply to access the services, the adoption of best practices in FAIR data management, the importance of their role in contributing to Europe's open data landscape and how this contributes to healthier marine and freshwater ecosystems.

Within the above target groups, specific stakeholder groups were identified via an initial mapping exercise in the first version of the C&D plan. These are detailed in Table 1 below,

¹ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

together with the relevant objectives, as well as multipliers and networks to reach these stakeholder groups. This stakeholder activity is an ongoing exercise, and will be further developed throughout the project with input from all partners, including through the clustering activities in Task 1.4. These stakeholders and activities also build on partners' own networks, including through previous projects and initiatives.

Table 1. Mapping of key stakeholder groups within the five main target groups, together with multiplier channels and specific communication and dissemination (C&D) objectives. Please note the list is not exhaustive.

Target Group	SG #	Stakeholder Group	Multipliers and Networks	C&D objectives
TG#1: Aquatic research scientists and academia, and scientific networks and projects	SG1	Academic researchers working in marine and freshwater domains, including researchers in vulnerable groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Partner Institutes -University marine and environmental institutes -Scientific networks (see SG4) -Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Raising awareness of AQUARIUS and integrated RI catalogue -Mobilising applications to TA Funding Calls -Targeting ECRs to engage in training opportunities
	SG2	Non-academic researchers in marine and freshwater domains, from, for example, public monitoring bodies, environmental management organisations, or research institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -National marine and environmental monitoring bodies -Regional Sea Conventions (OSPAR, HELCOM,...) -ICES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Promoting collaboration and building research capacity -Engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events) -Disseminating scientific outputs and KERS
	SG3	Relevant EU Mission Lighthouse projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -BlueMissionAA -BlueMission BANOS -EcoDaLLi -BlueMissionMed -DOORS -Mission Ocean and Waters Communication group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Raising awareness of AQUARIUS and integrated RI -Mobilising applications to TA Funding Calls from relevant scientists -Engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events) -Disseminating AQUARIUS outputs and KERS to support implementation activities
	SG4	EU and global scientific networks, organisations and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -European Marine Board -JPI Oceans -EurOcean -EuroMarine -Ocean Best Practices (OBPS) -UN Ocean Decade -ICES -OKEANO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its integrated RI -Promote TA Funding Calls and ECR opportunities -Disseminating scientific outputs and KERS -Promote engagement in

Target Group	SG #	Stakeholder Group	Multipliers and Networks	C&D objectives
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Ocean Decade Programme: Early Career Ocean Professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events)
TG#2: Relevant EU and global Research Infrastructures, long-term EU and global data services and Digital Twin of the Ocean	SG5	EU Research Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Partners networks (EMSO-ERIC, EMBRC, Danubius-RI, JERICO-RI, EuroFleets+, EUFAR) –LifeWatch ERIC –AQUACOSM –eLTER –ICOS ERIC –ENVRI-hub –RICH Europe –AMRIT –POLARIN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and integrated RI –Promote engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops –Implementation of best practices in RI integration –Uptake of new dataflows and data products from AQUARIUS RI –Dissemination and exploitation of AQUARIUS outputs and KERs
	SG6	Long-term EU and global data services and observing initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EMODnet –Copernicus Marine –SeaDataNet –PANGAEA –EuroGOOS –IODE –OBIS –OceanOPS –GOOS –ECO Ocean Data Sharing –UN DCO Ocean Observing –UN DCC Ocean Prediction –NOAA 	
	SG7	Digital twin & EOSC community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EDITO-Infra –EDITO-ModelLab –DITTO –Iliad –Blue-Cloud –TURTLE –DTO-BioFlow 	
TG#3: Industrial communities and SMEs	SG8	Industry representative groups, clusters, networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Blue Invest –Blue Skills –European Aquaculture Industry (EATiP) –Ocean Energy Europe –DBAN (Bulgaria, Ukraine, Georgia) –FUGRO –DEME –De Blauwe Cluster –Marine Industry Ireland Network –COFREPECHE 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its integrated RI –Promote TA calls and ECR opportunities to solicit applications –Promote engagement in relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops (e.g. brokerage events) –Dissemination and exploitation of AQUARIUS (and projects) KER
TG#4: Policy platforms, decision-makers and	SG9	EU institutions and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –EC DG MARE –EC DG ENV –EC DG R&I –DG DEFIS –DG CLIMA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its integrated RI –Promote engagement in

Target Group	SG #	Stakeholder Group	Multipliers and Networks	C&D objectives
funding bodies			–DG Regio –JPI Oceans (funding) –EU JRC –EU Mission Ocean and Waters –Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership	relevant AQUARIUS events and workshops –Dissemination and uptake of AQUARIUS policy brief
	SG10	National authorities/ government ministries with responsibility for marine/environmental management.	–Regional Sea Conventions (i.e. HELCOM, OSPAR, Black Sea Commission, UNEP-MAP)	
	SG11	International policy and initiatives, and international governance bodies	–CBD Secretariat –BBNJ Secretariat –IOC UNESCO	
TG#5: Wider (non-expert) society including citizen science groups	SG12	Citizen science groups	–EU4Ocean Coalition –Youth4Ocean	–Raise awareness of AQUARIUS and its societal relevance –Promote TA calls to include citizen science groups within projects –Dissemination of relevant AQUARIUS outputs and materials –Promote engagement with relevant events and workshops (e.g. brokerage event and final event)
	SG13	NGOs in marine and environmental arena	–European Citizen Science Association –SUBMON –WWF –SeasAtRisk –Surfriders –Wetlands International Europe –GreenPeace –Living Rivers Europe –Sea shepherd	
	SG14	Ocean literacy organisations/ advocates	–Ecsite –Nausicaa –Plastic Pirates EU	
	SG15	Media organisations	–EuroNews	
	SG16	Teachers and trainers	–Network of Blue Schools	

6. What: Key Messages

The following key concepts will be used to structure and articulate the different AQUARIUS communication messages, considering the specific needs and opportunities to which AQUARIUS responds.

Update C&D Plan Version II. As the second TA Funding Call closes at the end of October 2025, a number of these messages will no longer be used, and communication will be targeted towards the dissemination of the results/outputs of AQUARIUS and those of the TA Projects, as well as the continued promotion of the training opportunities for the remainder of the project.

Challenges and opportunities

- Europe has a rich landscape of marine and freshwater research infrastructures the integration of which can facilitate more collaborative and interconnected research and innovation to address urgent global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, marine pollution and ocean acidification.

- Considering the interconnectedness of our rivers, seas and ocean, there is a critical need for a more integrated and coordinated research infrastructure landscape.
- Europe’s research community (comprising scientists from academic, public bodies, industry and citizen science groups) may not be aware of the availability and potential of existing research infrastructures to advance research and innovation. Depending on their region or institutional capacity they may have difficulty accessing them, and/or lack the technical capacity to use them.

AQUARIUS added value

- For the first time AQUARIUS brings together 57 leading European research infrastructure services to facilitate more collaborative and systemic research that will contribute towards achieving healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems.
- AQUARIUS will launch two competitive Transnational Access Funding Calls. Through a robust and transparent evaluation process, AQUARIUS will select research and innovation projects that convincingly demonstrate how they will integrate research infrastructures and contribute to one of the goals of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters in a relevant Mission Lighthouse region.
- Through enabling more holistic research on marine and freshwater ecosystems, AQUARIUS will support the development phase of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, the European Green Deal, and international climate initiatives.
- AQUARIUS will serve the needs of research and innovation activities in the Mission Lighthouse regions: the Atlantic - Arctic, Baltic and North Sea, Danube and Black Sea, and Mediterranean Sea as well as in their major associated rivers (Danube, Elbe, Ebro or Burrishoole catchment).
- AQUARIUS will create a respected and trusted integrated ‘Aqua Infrastructure’ in Europe, representing the best of European research infrastructure and its international collaborators.

Examples of key messages tailored to specific target groups are outlined in the Table 2 below.

Table 2. Examples of key messages tailored to specific target groups

Target Group	Key messages
TG#1: Aquatic research scientists and academia, and scientific networks and projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –For the first time AQUARIUS brings together 57 leading European research infrastructure services to facilitate more collaborative and systemic research that will contribute towards achieving healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems. –AQUARIUS will launch two Transnational Access Funding Calls seeking proposals from research and innovation projects that can demonstrate how they will integrate multiple AQUARIUS infrastructures and respond to the call challenges. –AQUARIUS will provide free access to the infrastructure for scientists from the selected projects, including the necessary logistical, technical and scientific support. –AQUARIUS will prepare the new generation of marine and aquatic researchers through specific training in using the research infrastructures. –AQUARIUS will provide dedicated training on data management and data stewardship to ensure that researchers implement best practices in open

Target Group	Key messages
	<p>data, and are aware of existing European data infrastructures, services and tools for processing, documenting, and ingesting their newly collected data and data products.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> –AQUARIUS will launch internship Open Calls for early-career marine and freshwater scientists and technicians, including opportunities to participate in marine internships or floating universities. –AQUARIUS use case scenarios and success stories demonstrate a ‘systems thinking’ approach in the use of integrated research infrastructures to advance research and innovation that contributes to healthier and more sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems.
<p>TG#2: Relevant EU and global Research Infrastructures, long-term EU and global data services and Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – For the first time, AQUARIUS brings together diverse Research Infrastructures in Europe, demonstrating the benefits and highlighting best practices in integrating research infrastructures and contributing to the European Research Area. –Key European data infrastructures, data services and long-term EU and global initiatives, including digital twins, will benefit from the new data flows through enhanced FAIR data management. –AQUARIUS will contribute to strengthen the EU and global marine & freshwater digital knowledge system, including the future EU Digital Twin Ocean to inform policy objectives of the EU Green Deal, the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”, and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, as well as contributing to the European Partnership “A climate neutral, sustainable and productive Blue Economy”.
<p>TG#3: Industrial communities and SMEs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –For the first time AQUARIUS brings together 57 leading European research infrastructure services to facilitate more collaborative and systemic research and innovation relating to marine and freshwater ecosystems. –AQUARIUS Research Infrastructures are crucial enablers of research and technological innovation. –AQUARIUS will launch two Transnational Access Funding Calls to solicit proposals from research and innovation projects, including scientists from the private sector, that can demonstrate how they will integrate multiple AQUARIUS infrastructures and respond to the call challenges. –AQUARIUS will implement standardised access procedures, to facilitate open EU industrial research and innovation. –AQUARIUS will provide free and open access to new data flows, data products and project results.
<p>TG#4: Policy platforms, decision makers, and funding bodies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –AQUARIUS will enhance and further integrate research and innovation capacities in support of the development and implementation phases of the EU Mission ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030’, the European Green Deal, the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, and international climate initiatives. It will also be an essential component in achieving the European Digital Twin of the Ocean and the UN Decade for Ocean Sciences (2021-2030). –AQUARIUS Transnational Access Funding Calls will focus on key Mission Ocean Lighthouse Regions. –AQUARIUS will focus on challenge-driven and solution-focused research, that will benefit evidence-based marine and freshwater policies, with positive societal, environmental, technological and economic impacts for Europe. –The legacy of AQUARIUS will be consolidated into a strategic vision for the European Marine Research Infrastructures of the future, working in

Target Group	Key messages
	<p>tandem with participants and stakeholders towards ensuring better coordination and optimisation of RIs in the future.</p> <p>–The AQUARIUS strategic vision policy brief will guide policymakers and funders in their efforts towards further integration of services and future collaboration across European RIs.</p>
TG#5: Wider (non-expert) society including citizen science groups	<p>–Europe has a rich landscape of marine and freshwater Research Infrastructures which are essential for research and innovation that addresses urgent global challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, marine pollution and ocean acidification</p> <p>–AQUARIUS will launch two Transnational Access Funding Calls to solicit proposals from research and innovation projects, including citizen scientists, that can demonstrate how they will integrate multiple infrastructures and respond to the call challenges.</p> <p>–Citizen science groups are increasingly important as collectors and providers of FAIR environmental data, AQUARIUS adopts best practices in FAIR data management, and provides access to a range of resources and training materials to support open data practices.</p> <p>–Follow the projects! Find out how Europe’s incredible array of research infrastructure is used by scientists to explore, understand, and protect our marine and freshwater ecosystems.</p>

7. When: communication and dissemination phases

While communication and promotion of the project started at the onset of the project and continue throughout the lifetime of the project (i.e. entire four years), dissemination activities will begin with the publication of the first project results. Three overlapping communication and dissemination phases are planned, each with a distinct purpose, and within which there will be dedicated campaigns. These phases and campaigns are explained further below. Campaigns will be updated throughout the project.

7.1. Phase 1 – Awareness & Promotion (M1-M48)

Purpose: To raise awareness and visibility of AQUARIUS with all stakeholder groups.

Communication and dissemination material will be produced to introduce the project and highlight its activities to all five target groups. This phase will run throughout the entire project. Planned campaigns for the first eighteen months are indicated below. Others will be added as the project progresses. This phase includes highlighting news, activities, and outputs from both AQUARIUS and from the successful Transnational Access Projects, as well as activities in the broader landscape in which AQUARIUS sits.

Planned communication campaigns supporting Phase 1:

- AQUARIUS kicks-off
- Get to know AQUARIUS, its partners, objectives and upcoming activities
- Launch of the AQUARIUS online searchable Research Infrastructure Catalogue
- Pre-launch of first Transnational Access Funding Call
- The role of Research Infrastructures in the European Research Area
- Meet our Research Infrastructure providers
- Meet our successful Transnational Access Projects (Calls 1 & 2)
- Follow our Transnational Access Projects’ campaigns (Calls 1 & 2)

7.2. Phase 2 – Outreach & Engagement (M7-M48)

Purpose: To promote active engagement with AQUARIUS opportunities.

This phase will focus on targeting stakeholders with specific ‘calls to action’ to mobilise their involvement with AQUARIUS activities. A significant focus of this phase will be to solicit applications to the Transnational Access Funding Calls via two dedicated outreach and engagement campaigns (one for each call). As such, the most important target groups for this phase will be research scientists from TG#1 – TG#3, and citizen scientists from TG#5. This phase will also highlight the AQUARIUS training opportunities, particularly those for early-career researchers (ECR), i.e., the calls for marine internships and floating universities. It will also encourage registration for other AQUARIUS events (e.g., brokerage events, targeted meetings with industry, and webinars). While the main thrust of this activity will be from month seven to the close of the second Transnational Access Calls, the ECR and training opportunities and other opportunities for engagement (including engagement with the activities of the Transnational Access Projects, where relevant) will run throughout the project.

Planned campaigns supporting Phase 2:

- Register for our brokerage events
- Transnational Access Funding Call 1 (Sep 2024-Feb 2025): Themes, Eligibility and Evaluation criteria, Use cases, Learn to use the call platform, Apply now!
- Transnational Access Funding Call 2 (Jun-Oct 2025): Themes, Eligibility and Evaluation criteria, Use cases, Learn to use the call platform, Apply now!
- Calling all early-career researchers and marine technicians:
 - Apply to marine internships
 - Apply to floating universities
- Join our webinar(s) on FAIR data management
- Join our webinar to learn about the Blue Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)
- Join our technical training webinars
- Visit the Training Hub on the website
- Join our final event

7.3. Phase 3 – Uptake (M7-M48)

Purpose: To disseminate project key exploitable results (KER) and outputs (deliverables, factsheets, infographics, training webinars, data flows and products), both from AQUARIUS itself and from the successful Transnational Access Projects as a first step towards their exploitation (this will be further planned in Task 7.3).

Project outputs and results (KERs) will be disseminated to the relevant stakeholder groups who can exploit, from TG#1, TG#2, TG#3, TG#4 and TG#5.

Planned campaigns supporting Phase 3:

- AQUARIUS data gaps report is now available
- AQUARIUS call priorities report is now available
- AQUARIUS resources on FAIR data management are now available
- New dataflows are available
- Training webinars are available
- Transnational Access Project results are available
- Launch of the AQUARIUS policy brief
- AQUARIUS legacy film is available

All phases will be supported by planned and targeted content shared via the various channels (described further in Sections 8, 9, and 10 below) and, where relevant, implementing the pay-per-view campaign to broaden outreach or to target specific audiences.

Update C&D Plan Version II. Communication and dissemination activities have been implemented across all three phases in the first 18 months and will continue over the remainder of the project. Significant effort was expended in the first 18 months in Phase 1 to raise the visibility of AQUARIUS as a new project in the transnational access landscape before the launch of the first funding call in November 2024.

The primary focus of Phase 2 was the launch of two dedicated outreach and engagement campaigns for each of the two funding calls. These are summarised in Tables 6 and 7 (below).

As Call 2 opens in early September 2025, outreach and engagement activities were initiated in May 2025 to create awareness for the call in advance of the summer months. In the period between the first Call closing and the launch of the campaign for the second Call, the focus moved to the early career training opportunities. These will be picked up again after the closure of the second call, as will the opportunities for technical and data management training.

Phase 3 was initiated in month seven with the publication of the first AQUARIUS deliverables. All public deliverables are made available via the website resources page and Zenodo. This dissemination phase will continue and include the outputs arising from the funded projects, as they become available.

8. How: Tools and Materials

8.1. Project branding & visual identity

The first step in any project communication and dissemination strategy is to create a strong and recognisable visual identity through common branding on all communication materials, channels, activities and outputs. The brand identity for AQUARIUS is based on the project logo.

8.1.1. The AQUARIUS logo

The AQUARIUS logo was developed and evolved during the project proposal stage in discussion with partners (Figure 3). The agreed logo (Figure 4) conveys the land-river-ocean connection of aquatic ecosystems through an abstract visual. The colours also reflect the different ecosystem components relevant to AQUARIUS, from land (green), river and coastal (shades of blue), and ocean (blue wave). Finally, the dashed lines represent the technological aspect of AQUARIUS.

Figure 3. The development process of the AQUARIUS logo

Figure 4. The AQUARIUS logo

8.1.2. Branding guidelines

A user-friendly branding guideline (Figure 5) was shared with the project consortium at the onset of the project, together with a toolkit of branded templates (Word, PowerPoint), to ensure that the integrity of the AQUARIUS brand extends through all visual communications, documents and reports, creating consistency in communications and recognition for AQUARIUS.

Figure 5. AQUARIUS branding guidelines

8.1.3. AQUARIUS tagline

The following tagline was developed at the start of the project for integration in AQUARIUS communication channels and materials.

Integrating Research Infrastructures - Connecting Scientists - Enabling Transnational Access
For healthy and sustainable marine and freshwater ecosystems

8.1.4. Visual background/visualiser

A key visualizer was created as a background for PowerPoint slide decks and as a virtual background that can be used during webinars and videoconferences in e.g. Zoom, to promote a strong brand identity through various communication activities.

Figure 6. AQUARIUS visualiser

In keeping with the contractual requirements of Horizon Europe funding, the following funding acknowledgment, disclaimer statement, and EU emblem (Figure 7) are a staple of all branded communication material and appear in the footer of templates and materials (flyers, posters, etc).

Figure 7. Acknowledgement of funding statement and disclaimer

8.2. Communication and dissemination materials

The following materials have been developed to support the implementation of communication and dissemination activities.

Branded materials

To promote AQUARIUS at events and workshops, some branded materials (Figure 8), carrying the AQUARIUS logo, QR code and/or website URL have been designed and ordered. Currently, these include stickers for laptops, AQUARIUS pins, USB-A to Micro-B and Type-C USB lanyards, bamboo pens, and chocolates.

In choosing these materials, consideration is given to the sustainability of the materials used, their potential usefulness to receivers and effectiveness as promotional materials (QR codes and URL where possible).

To mark the online kick-off event a “goodie bag” was sent to each partner to promote a sense of identity and raise the visibility of AQUARIUS within their own networks.

Figure 8. AQUARIUS branded materials

Update C&D Plan Version II. The original stickers in Figure 8 were redesigned for a stronger brand identity and to more clearly highlight the AQUARIUS Transnational Access opportunity (Figure 9, right). An extra sticker was designed for the promotion of the training opportunities (Figure 9, left).

Figure 9. AQUARIUS updated stickers

Project PowerPoint slide deck

A general project presentation has been produced in PowerPoint for consortium partners to disseminate AQUARIUS information at conferences, events and meetings (Figure 10). It provides a comprehensive overview of the project, the consortium, objectives, work plan, activities and opportunities. It can be used as a stand-alone presentation to introduce AQUARIUS at events and meetings, for dissemination material, and individual slides can

be incorporated into other presentations needed for specific purposes and audiences. Key slides are updated and added as the project progresses.

Figure 10. AQUARIUS introductory slide-deck

Update C&D Plan Version II. Additional slides have been made available to complement the slide deck, in particular to promote the Transnational Access Funding Calls and Training Opportunities.

Brochure

A general AQUARIUS project brochure has been produced to introduce AQUARIUS to all target groups (Figure 11). It contains summary information on the project's key facts (funding, consortium, timeline), and focuses on the main aspects of AQUARIUS, the integration of research infrastructures and the Transnational Access Funding Calls. The brochure will be available in both digital and print versions (in a fold-out format) and include the website QR code.

Update C&D Plan Version II. The first version of the brochure was updated slightly to reflect the closure of TA Call 1 and to include an updated map that included all the AQUARIUS virtual Labs and Data Centres (see infographic, below).

FRONT

OPEN

BACK

FULL OPEN

Figure 11. AQUARIUS fold-out brochure

Infographic

Several infographics will be developed throughout the AQUARIUS project as visual and user-friendly ways to present more complex information. The first infographic (Figure 12) focused on the AQUARIUS Research Infrastructure portfolio, to explain the categories, numbers and geographic location of the 57 AQUARIUS research infrastructures. It included a QR code linking to the AQUARIUS website. Printed copies of the infographic (500 units) have been produced for distribution at key conferences, events and meetings. It is also available for download via the website.

Update C&D Plan Version II. The infographic was updated to include Category 9 - Data Centres and Virtual Labs (as all this information became available). This updated infographic was shared on social media channels and on the website. The updated map was also included in the brochure and poster.

Figure 12. AQUARIUS infographic

Factsheets/Flyers

Two AQUARIUS factsheets will be produced, one for each Transnational Access Funding Call, summarising the key information on challenge areas, eligibility criteria, and directing to the detailed webpage via a QR code. Additional factsheets will detail the AQUARIUS data flows and the Transnational Access Projects, with others developed as needed.

Update C&D Plan Version II. Initial plans had been to produce a detailed factsheet for each Funding Call, however, it was decided instead to create eye-catching “flyers” for both physical and electronic dissemination. These contain simple overview information and direct applicants to the detailed information on the website (Figure 14). They were/are disseminated as A5 flyers at events and as images in emails, newsletters, and on social media.

Additional factsheets will detail the AQUARIUS data flows and the Transnational Access Projects, with others developed as needed. Factsheet templates were produced to collect summary information for each of the successful Transnational Access projects. WP4 collected all the information, which was then published as a dedicated webpage/factsheet for each project on the AQUARIUS website. For example: <https://aquarius-ri.eu/transnational-access-call-1/abacus-2026/>.

Figure 13 Flyers for dissemination to highlight the AQUARIUS Transnational Access calls.

Figure 14. Dedicated webpages developed with WP3 to provide all the detailed factual information on the respective Transnational Access Funding Calls.

Poster

A general poster has been produced to support activities in the early phases of the project, to explain the AQUARIUS concept and the opportunities it offers, with an emphasis on the Transnational Access Funding Calls (Figure 15, left). The poster is scalable to fit various requirements, ensuring its suitability for conferences and meetings.

Update C&D Plan Version II. Variant(s) of the poster were produced for events. A targeted poster was produced to promote the opportunities for early career scientists and technicians (Figure 15, example right).

Figure 15. AQUARIUS posters

Pull-up banners

Two pull-up banners have been produced for AQUARIUS events (Figure 16), specifically the first brokerage events.

Update C&D Plan Version II. These were updated to indicate the closure of the first Funding Call, featuring updated visuals. Others will be created as the project progresses.

Figure 16. AQUARIUS pull-up banner

Videos

Two short (two to five-minute) videos will be produced during the project. The first promotional project video will be produced by month 12, and feature short interviews with key project partners, images of the research infrastructures and animations of AQUARIUS visuals and infographics. A second, legacy video will be produced towards the end of the project. Video shorts will be produced to promote events and project highlights on social media throughout the project's lifecycle, particularly in advance of each Transnational Access Funding Call, serving as "call to action" teasers for social media. Edits from interviews with consortium members and recipients of funding calls may be considered to

promote the impact of success stories across social media, YouTube and suitable events offering video walls.

Update C&D Plan Version II. The first of the two planned videos (promotional and legacy) was created to coincide with the launch of the first TA Funding Call (November 2024) and focused very much on the Transnational Access opportunities in AQUARIUS. While there had been an opportunity to interview the WP lead partners at the AQUARIUS brokerage event, it was decided to use the chance of the first in-person General Assembly (February 2025) to interview some of the other partners and RI providers and create an updated promo video that told more of the “story” of AQUARIUS. This video was produced and released in April 2025.

In addition, several teaser videos have been produced for social media, containing short interviews with partners to highlight aspects of AQUARIUS or blog posts (the RI catalogue, the transnational activity, outcomes of TA Funding Call 1, the Transnational Access Platform, ...).

All videos have been published on the AQUARIUS YouTube channel, promoted on social media, and in some cases screened at event booths.

Figure 17. AQUARIUS video images

9. Where: Channels

9.1. Project website

The AQUARIUS website at AQUARIUS-RI.eu is much more than a project website. In addition to being the primary source of all information on AQUARIUS and a key media channel for promoting the opportunities offered by AQUARIUS, and supporting the uptake of results (from both AQUARIUS and the successful Transnational Access Projects), it has the following specific purposes:

1. Host the interactive AQUARIUS Research Infrastructure Catalogue, containing images, maps and detailed factsheets for each of the research infrastructures and data centres (provided by WP4);
2. Source of information on Transnational Access Funding (provided by WP2 and 4):
 - Information on Transnational Access Funding Calls, including challenge areas, eligibility criteria, evaluation process, and example use cases
 - Gateway to the Transnational Access Platform.
3. AQUARIUS Training Hub – Technical Material Repository (provided by WP5)
 - How to use the Transnational Access Platform
 - Research infrastructure technical training materials/links
 - Opportunities for early career scientists and technicians (floating universities and marine internships)
 - Data management and use of Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment

- Links to resources related to the 'healthy waters and ocean'
- 4. Link to AQUARIUS Data Dashboard and relevant resources, including data management plans (provided by WP6)
- 5. 'Meet the AQUARIUS Transnational Access projects' page
- 6. Central source of all AQUARIUS outputs and dissemination materials

The website also includes a form where visitors can sign up to the AQUARIUS newsletter, as well as a 'contact us' email and direct links to AQUARIUS social media.

The first version of the website was developed for the online AQUARIUS kick-off meeting (April 2024) to provide an official information channel for interested stakeholders alerted by social media posts. It launched with general information on the project, contact details, and call-to-action buttons to encourage newsletter subscriptions.

Traffic to the website will be primarily driven through social media and strategically placed banners on partner websites, leveraging the opportunity for promotion when the Transnational Access Funding Calls open. In addition, effective meta tags for Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) have been implemented on each page.

Google Analytics is being used to monitor site traffic. Statistics will be assessed regularly to ensure the numbers support targeted Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). If not, action will be taken to increase visibility via social media and/or other relevant channels.

Update C&D Plan Version II. A substantial upgrade to the website was delivered as part of D7.3 (M6) to meet the purposes listed above and to prepare for the launch of the first TA Funding Call in November 2024. The webpage has since continued to see significant upgrades to coincide with project activities.

- The homepage now has two sliding banners to highlight the research infrastructures and the projects funded in TA Funding Call 1.
- Before and during each TA Call opening period, a banner is visible on all pages of the website to highlight the Call.
- The research infrastructure catalogue provides an incredible resource for call applicants and for wider users to showcase European research infrastructures. An interactive map highlights the research infrastructures available for the respective sea regions. <https://aquarius-ri.eu/research-infrastructures-catalogue/>
- The Transnational Access page contains overview information on both Calls, with a side-bar menu providing links to detailed information on each call, the eligibility criteria, how to apply, evaluation and selection procedures, funding conditions, example use case scenarios, additional resources and templates, and a detailed FAQ page. <https://aquarius-ri.eu/access/>
- The training page links to the "training hub" and the "training opportunities" pages. The former provides access to the "research infrastructures technical training material", "AQUARIUS webinars", "data management and analytics" resources, and resources relevant to "health oceans and waters" (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/training-resources/traininghub/>). The "training opportunities" page provides access to the information and application forms for the training opportunities for early career scientists. <https://aquarius-ri.eu/training-resources/training-opportunities/>
- Projects funded in TA Call 1 are highlighted with summary information in dedicated pages accessible via an overview page, each with a dedicated page, accessible through the overview page, which also shows the timeline for implementation. <https://aquarius-ri.eu/transnational-access-call-1/>
- The AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard is now accessible via the "Data" item on the toolbar.

- All project resources (e.g. deliverables and other resources) are accessible via the “project resources” item on the dropdown menu of the “About Aquarius” main menu item. <https://aquarius-ri.eu/aquarius-ri-downloads/>
- A “News and More” menu item links to the news page which is regularly updated (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/news-events/>), the AQUARIUS partners blog series (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/aquarius-stories/>), and the newsletter archives (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/newsletter-archive/>).
- Finally, two additional menu items were added to the main menu, an FAQ page (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/faq/>) and a link to the gallery (<https://aquarius-ri.eu/aquarius-gallery/>).

Website analytics show significant traffic to the website (12K users), with the geographic breakdown showing users visiting from across the globe. The most viewed pages after the home page are the “Research Infrastructure Catalogue”, the “TA Calls Access” page, and the “training opportunities”, in that order.

The website will be continuously maintained and updated as the main point of access to all resources and opportunities and to support the ongoing storytelling.

Figure 18. Screenshots from the AQUARIUS website (update C&D Plan version II)

Figure 19

Page title and screen class +		↓ Views	Active users	Views per active user	Average engagement time per active user	Event count All events ▾
Total		59,971 100% of total	12,281 100% of total	4.88 Avg 0%	2m 14s Avg 0%	169,457 100% of total
1	Integrating Research Infrastructures – Connecting Scientists – Enabling Transnational Access - AQUARIUS	6,706 (11.18%)	2,989 (24.34%)	2.24	32s	20,867 (12.31%)
2	Research Infrastructures Catalogue - AQUARIUS	5,201 (8.67%)	2,252 (18.34%)	2.31	1m 31s	14,897 (8.79%)
3	Research infrastructure can be offered through transnational, remote and virtual access. - AQUARIUS	5,010 (8.35%)	2,277 (18.54%)	2.20	1m 09s	14,371 (8.48%)
4	Open Call Internships - AQUARIUS	4,034 (6.73%)	2,558 (20.83%)	1.58	46s	12,532 (7.4%)
5	Seabed Mapping Training Programme - AQUARIUS	2,909 (4.85%)	1,612 (13.13%)	1.80	47s	9,243 (5.45%)
6	Training Opportunities - AQUARIUS	1,788 (2.98%)	912 (7.43%)	1.96	24s	5,094 (3.01%)
7	Summer Schools - AQUARIUS	1,695 (2.83%)	961 (7.83%)	1.76	53s	4,841 (2.86%)
8	TA Call 2: Super-integrated Lighthouse Call - AQUARIUS	1,598 (2.66%)	963 (7.84%)	1.66	33s	4,761 (2.81%)
9	Training - AQUARIUS	1,593 (2.66%)	714 (5.81%)	2.23	19s	4,117 (2.43%)
10	Eligibility criteria - AQUARIUS	1,533 (2.56%)	934 (7.61%)	1.64	1m 01s	4,206 (2.48%)

Figure 20

Figure 21 Google Analytics of the AQUARIUS website for the last 12 months, showing from top to bottom: Number of users/visitors to the website, most viewed pages, and geographic spread of users.

9.2. Social media

Social media is a vital channel to support communication through each phase of the Communication and Dissemination Plan. Independent social media accounts have been established for AQUARIUS under the “project” category on X, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram. LinkedIn will be the primary channel in the first six months. A short Slido poll, launched during the kick-off meeting, indicated that partners considered LinkedIn as the most relevant channel to reach AQUARIUS’ targeted stakeholders. Posts will also be published on X, and engagement level will be monitored. Facebook and Instagram will be activated to reach the wider societal audience. A YouTube channel has also been created for AQUARIUS webinars and video material.

The social media strategy involves attracting interest from stakeholders through visually compelling graphics and engaging content that describes project information and

activities, with a focus on outreach at events. Social media is an essential channel for promoting the Transnational Access Funding Calls; vigorous campaigns have been developed and implemented to facilitate the promotion of the two calls (supported also by the Pay Per Click campaign to maximise the reach to target audiences, where relevant).

While the project name should always be written in full caps, the everyday use of the word 'Aquarius' and limitations on social media handles required the development of different handles (as outlined below).

Table 3. AQUARIUS social media channels

Channel	Link
Twitter	https://x.com/AquariusRii
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/aquarius-ri/
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/aquarius__ri
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/Aquarius-Ri
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@AQUARIUS-RI-q5w

Social media approach

AQUARIUS adopts best practices in social media to promote engagement, according to the following guiding principles:

- Consider the purpose of the post: Who is it aimed at and what do we want to achieve. Is the tone and message appropriate?
- Be informative and add value: Teaser posts to create awareness and trigger interest in upcoming activities/opportunities. Posts to highlight new information. 'Calls to action' to engage in AQUARIUS activities or events.
- Drive traffic to the AQUARIUS website: Link to relevant material on the AQUARIUS website, e.g. Research Infrastructure Catalogue, Transnational Access Calls platform, application forms for training activities, project results and outputs.
- Be engaging: Lead with an interesting, relevant question or statement that relates to the content of the post.
- Use compelling visuals: Photography, animated visuals, infographics, eye-catching posters.
- Optimal timing of posts: Leverage relevant dates in the calendar or current trends.
- Tag handles with large and relevant communities.
- Use hashtags: Customised for nature of content and specific stakeholders.
- Use emojis that are easy to understand and relevant for posts.
- When retweeting content, always retweet with a quote and making the relevance to AQUARIUS clear.
- Consistency: Maintaining engaging content on a regular basis.
- Establish a strategy for comments: Reply in a positive and timely manner. Block spam and refer questions to subject matter experts as appropriate.

In the first six months of the project, AQUARIUS social media focused on introducing the project and rolling out teaser posts to trigger interest in the upcoming launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue and Transnational Access Funding Calls. The purpose was to build awareness, test hashtags, gain followers, and identify early influencers.

Update C&D Plan Version II. From September 2024 onwards, social media has focused on the AQUARIUS activities and opportunities, with most effort focusing on the two Transnational Access Funding Calls outreach and engagement campaigns, as well as the training opportunities for early career scientists. Significant effort is invested in creating informative and visually appealing posts that stay on message and within the scope of AQUARIUS.

LinkedIn remains the primary communication channel for AQUARIUS, where the target audience for the TA Calls and training opportunities are active. It has been highly successful, having gained over 2.5k followers in 18 months. Engagement with X was gradually discontinued in late 2024/early 2025 following a poll with partners at the second AQUARIUS General Assembly.

To ensure consistency of AQUARIUS messaging and style, and make it easier for partners to help promote AQUARIUS, social media toolkits are prepared and shared with partners to help promote important activities. These have included the launch of the Research Infrastructure catalogue, the first brokerage event, and the TA Funding Call campaigns (as part of the dedicated TA Calls communication toolkits). The social media toolkits include messages, images, hashtags, and tags.

Figure 22. Growth in AQUARIUS LinkedIn followers over the course of the project, from March 2024 to July 2025.

Content territories of the AQUARIUS project

To strategically reach targeted stakeholder audiences within each social media channel with relevant content, and identify opportunities that can be leveraged to promote AQUARIUS, the AQUARIUS “content territories” have been scoped and defined below in Figure 23. This exercise will guide the content strategy.

Figure 23. AQUARIUS "content territories" informing the scope of and opportunities for AQUARIUS social media communication and dissemination activities.

Hashtag library and mapping key stakeholders in the social media landscape

The most popular hashtags connected to the AQUARIUS content territories have been researched, and a hashtag library has been developed (Appendix 1). The use of relevant hashtags increases content exposure, boosting the opportunity to engage with defined stakeholders and attracting new stakeholders.

Partners LinkedIn and X handles and hashtags

The consortium partners have a well-established presence in the social media networks (Appendix 2) and have been very engaged with AQUARIUS social media posts, helping to increase their impact.

9.3. Scientific journals and magazines

Scientific peer-reviewed papers produced by AQUARIUS partners or those of the Transnational Access Projects will be a key means of disseminating scientific or technical project results. Relevant magazines (e.g. trade, societal) will be targeted for articles and other content to reach other wider audiences.

9.4. Newsletters

The AQUARIUS newsletter was launched in September 2024, i.e. month 7 of the project, to capitalise on the launch of the Research Infrastructure catalogue, brokerage events and availability of first key Deliverables. The newsletter is published on a quarterly schedule through the lifecycle of the project. Each issue will convey ongoing project developments, including news on the Transnational Access Funding Calls, training opportunities, a summary of meetings and upcoming events, and will highlight success stories and blogs. It is distributed via Eudonet, a GDPR-compliant tool and stakeholder management database. Recipients subscribe to the newsletter from the website via a registration form. Call-to-action buttons creating awareness for newsletter subscription are regularly posted on social media and included in communication material, i.e. PowerPoint templates, posters, flyers.

Update C&D Plan Version II. To date (August 2025), there are 260 subscribers to the AQUARIUS newsletter. Three newsletters have been published, as well as two “news flashes” (Figure 24), the latter of which are short pieces with specific “calls to action” or highlighting important AQUARIUS activities, e.g., launch of the first Funding Call, countdown to opening of second Funding Call (ahead of the summer period) and important updates to eligibility criteria in Funding Call 2. Partners can easily forward these newsflashes to their networks via email. All of the newsletters are available via the archive <https://aquarius-ri.eu/newsletter-archive/>.

Figure 24. Newsletter and newsflash

Figure 25 Screenshot of the AQUARIUS newsletter dashboard showing the number of subscribers, their sea basin, and sector.

9.5. Blogs and success stories

Blogs are an effective mechanism for storytelling and can foster a spirit of personal connection and engagement with stakeholder audiences thus maximising impact. A minimum of one blog per quarter will be developed and published on the AQUARIUS website. Blogs may take on the format of interviews, personal narratives and traditional articles (targeted towards specific stakeholder groups) and will focus on various themes connected to the project activities, scientific domains, call results and more. Consortium

members will be encouraged to share their stories through blogs with editorial support provided by WP7.

Success Stories, comprehensive science blogs, will be developed to demonstrate the importance of enabling transnational access to research infrastructures and to promote the opportunities and achievements of the recipients of the funding grants. The Success Stories will all demonstrate how AQUARIUS activities are addressing societal challenges through its work to integrate, and facilitate access to, research infrastructures.

Update C&D Plan Version II. To date (August 2025) five partner blogs have been published, designed to coincide with particular activities or opportunities (launch of the research infrastructure catalogue, launch of Call 1, training opportunities (x 2), updates to Funding Call 2). All of the blogs are promoted on social media and available via the website: <https://aquarius-ri.eu/aquarius-stories/>. These blogs will be extended to include the funded projects in the next phase of AQUARIUS.

9.6. Open Science Platforms

Scientific papers arising from AQUARIUS work and that of the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Projects, together with relevant deliverables and outputs, will be disseminated via open science platforms, communities, and repositories (e.g., Zenodo), including EOSC via Blue-Cloud. The website will host a page describing papers referencing AQUARIUS, with links to where they can be accessed (as they become available). These papers will be promoted on social media and their publications will be communicated in the newsletter.

Update C&D Plan Version II. A dedicated AQUARIUS Zenodo community was established early in the project by the project manager. All public project outputs are uploaded to Zenodo as they become available. To date, there are 16 records, from which there have been a total of 460 downloads.
<https://zenodo.org/communities/aquariusri/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

9.7. Mailing lists and networks

Promotion and communication of the launch of the Research Infrastructure Catalogue, the Transnational Access Funding Calls, and training opportunities, have and will continue to be activated through partner mailing lists and those established in other Transnational Access Projects such as Eurofleets 1,2 and Eurofleets+, JERICO, AssemblePlus and existing programmes, for example those managed by EMSO ERIC, EMBRC, amongst others.

Update C&D Plan Version II. To promote the launch of the calls, draft emails were prepared as part of the communication toolkit. Partners were invited to share these with their contacts and networks for broader dissemination. Newsletters of multipliers were also targeted, and the Funding Calls have been featured in the newsletters and of the European Marine Board, JPI Oceans, ENVRI plus, EMODnet, Blue Cluster, Mission Ocean, amongst others. The TA Funding Calls have also been featured in two distinct listservs related to biodiversity and algae research.
<https://zenodo.org/communities/aquariusri/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

9.8. Training workshops, conferences & events

Workshops, meetings and events throughout the AQUARIUS project will provide opportunities for communication, knowledge exchange and targeted dissemination activities. Table 4 below provides an overview of the types of meetings and events with an indication of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). As the project progresses, the table will be completed and updated.

Update C&D Plan Version II. AQUARIUS has organised several brokerage events and training webinars in the current period. Partners have also been very active in participating to third-party meetings and events to promote the project and disseminate outputs. A project “Communication and Dissemination Activity Log” maintains a log of all such activities and is included in Appendix 1. The KPIs are reported in Tables 4 and 5. In total, partners have so far attended 39 events across Europe, engaging with audiences in 15 countries, targeting approximately 4,000 participants in total.

Table 4. Workshops, conferences and events organised or attended by AQUARIUS partners

Event type	Description & objectives	Target Groups	KPI	Status M18 (August 2025)
Brokerage events	To launch the RI Catalogue, to raise awareness of TA Calls, including presentations from WP and networking sessions for researchers.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	+500 stakeholders at brokerage event	3 in-person brokerage events & 1 online brokerage webinar. +500 stakeholders engaged
Webinars	To highlight AQUARIUS Calls and provide training in the use of the Transnational Access Platform	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	+200 registered participants	2 webinars have been held to date. Webinar 1 (100 participants), Webinar 2 (50 participants)
Training workshops	Floating academy/universities, training workshops, summer schools, internship programmes	1,3 and 5	+50 scientists trained	One training webinar on AQUARIUS FAIR data management has been held. +40 participants
Conferences	Project partners will participate in at least 20 conferences, exhibitions & trade fairs throughout EU and non-EU countries.	1,3,4,5	+20 events	+30
Targeted meetings	Targeted meetings with relevant trade associations to share the results of the project with blue economy SMEs & industry.	3	+5 meetings	0
Final event	To showcase final results & future developments, and planned alongside a relevant large-scale European event or in conjunction with sister projects, and recorded for further dissemination & impact.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	+50 participants	0

AQUARIUS EVENTS

- Attended **39 events** across Europe
- Engaging with audiences in **15 countries**

- 8th IAHR Europe Congress -Lisbon, Portugal
- International Underwater Glider Conference -Gothenburg, Sweden
- 26th European Research Vessel Operators ERVO Meeting -Vigo, Spain
- Jerico-S3 Final General Assembly -Brest, France
- MarBlue AQUARIUS Brokerage Event -Constanta, Romania
- SLU AQUA Research Collegium -Lysekil Sweden
- HYPERSPECTRAL 2024 -Noordwijk, Netherlands
- Project Marine Management and Climate (Nordic Council) -Goteburg, Sweden
- Swedish Marine Research Days 2024 -Kalmar, Sweden
- AQUARIUS Training Webinar -Online

Figure 26. A timeline overview of where partners highlighted AQUARIUS at various events.

9.9. European Commission channels and tools

European Commission and Horizon Europe dissemination channels and tools will be leveraged to further promote AQUARIUS and disseminate outputs. To this end, the following will be explored and used as appropriate:

- EU Research and Innovation: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/projects_en
- Horizon Magazine: <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/horizon-magazine>
- Horizon Results Booster: <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/> - Ended in October 2024: follow-on services will be explored
- Open Research Europe: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

Update C&D Plan Version II. AQUARIUS signed the Mission Charter and was accepted as an endorsed action under the Charter, which fosters stakeholder collaboration to drive transformative change. In addition, AQUARIUS WP7 representatives joined the Mission Ocean Communication Working Group in mid-2024, but were later advised that the group was restricted to projects funded under the Mission programme.

10. AQUARIUS Communication and Dissemination: planning and implementation

The earlier sections of this document explain the AQUARIUS approach to communication and dissemination, detailing target stakeholders and objectives, key messages, timing (phases), tools, materials and channels.

This approach is summarised in Table 5, below, together with KPIs for tracking progress.

WP7 leads the design and implementation of the AQUARIUS communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, with all AQUARIUS partners contributing to dissemination and communication activities (with support from WP7) to ensure the timely promotion of activities and dissemination of outputs.

Monthly WP7 meetings are held with partners to coordinate this project-wide activity to co-design and share new communication products, highlight upcoming events and opportunities for AQUARIUS, and to identify important project activities and outputs for dissemination and communication.

The AQUARIUS SharePoint facility implemented by the project coordinator contains the “communication toolkit,” which includes all the branded templates and materials that have been developed to date, so that partners can promote the project and disseminate outputs in a consistent style.

Finally, AQUARIUS partner networks and the portfolio of related projects to which they participate represent an extensive network of target stakeholders for AQUARIUS. They are actively used to promote and disseminate AQUARIUS opportunities, activities and results.

Update C&D Plan Version II. AQUARIUS WP7 has held monthly online meetings. These meetings are well attended by partners, providing an opportunity to exchange communication and dissemination updates, identify target events, and gather feedback on material development. Monitoring of KPIs shows that AQUARIUS has either already reached targeted KPIs or is on track to do so by project end. In some cases where KPIs are low, these can be explained by the stage of the project.

10.1. Communication and dissemination content calendar

A detailed “communication and dissemination content calendar” is developed and maintained by WP7 to plan all communication and dissemination activities and related content. Project milestones, deliverables, activities and outputs guide this.

Update C&D Plan Version II. The activities for the first 18 months of AQUARIUS were detailed in the first version of this document. For the remainder of the project, a high-level editorial calendar has been developed to allow for confirmation of activities on which communication and dissemination activities must be based (Table 8). These include the status of projects funded under each Call, their launch, activity, and results; upcoming and ongoing training opportunities and webinars; meetings and events that partners will organise or participate in, as well as project outputs and finally, the possibility of a third Call. This calendar will be further detailed as information becomes available.

11. Post-project and AQUARIUS legacy

The AQUARIUS website will remain live for a period of five years after the project completion for the ongoing dissemination of key exploitable results, project information, including the archive of blogs, newsletters, videos, training tutorials and other items.

The legacy of AQUARIUS will be considered in the development of the AQUARIUS legacy video (D7.5) and the Policy Brief (D7.7). Key events and conferences will be identified to disseminate project results in the immediate year following the project's completion, and partners will be identified to disseminate results going forward, ensuring the exploitation of AQUARIUS results and the project's legacy.

12. Next steps

This document has outlined the revision of the Communication and Dissemination Plan for AQUARIUS.

Table 5. Overview of AQUARIUS communication and dissemination phases, summarising target groups, objectives, campaigns, types of supporting content, channels and associated KPIs

Phase	TG	Objectives	Campaigns	Content type	Channels	KPIs	
						Target (month 48)	Status (month 18)
Awareness & Promotion (M1-M48)	TG#1	Raise awareness of AQUARIUS, its activities and the societal value of the project.	AQUARIUS kicks-off	Social media posts	Website (news, blogs)	1 toolkit	1 general toolkit, 1 toolkit on the brokerage event, 2 promotional toolkits to promote TA
	TG#2		Get to know AQUARIUS and its people	Presentations	Social media		
	TG#3		What's coming in AQUARIUS (two TA calls, integrated RI – catalogue)	Brochure	Newsletter		
	TG#4		Meet our funded projects	Factsheet	Events	2 roll -up banners	4 roll-ups
	TG#5			Posters	Meetings	+3000 visits to the AQUARIUS project website	66,245 page views; 26,228 sessions; 14k engaged sessions; 13k total users;
			Blog	E-mailing lists	+500 followers (Social media)	2,505 LinkedIn followers, 119 X followers, 43 Instagram followers	
			Interviews		10 newsletters	4 newsletters, 3 newsflashes	
					+2000 brochures distributed	740+ brochures distributed (online + physical); 300 flyers distributed	
					+500 downloads infographics & factsheets	129 downloads from website, but viewed widely on LinkedIn Impressions 2581, clicks 183	
				+500 views for 4 videos	797 (You Tube); 11,473 (LinkedIn)		
				+5000 clicks in PPC campaigns	1,911 clicks		
Outreach & Engagement (M7-M48)	TG#1	To mobilise relevant stakeholder groups to apply to the two TA calls.	Register to AQUARIUS brokerage event.	Social media posts	Website (news, blogs)	3000 researchers targeted	3000+ researchers targeted
	TG#3		Explore our RI catalogue.	Presentations	Social media	500+ citizen science groups contacted	200+ citizen science groups contacted (email campaign to citizen science organisations, LinkedIn)
	TG#5			Posters	Newsletter		
				Flyers/leaflets			

Phase	TG	Objectives	Campaigns	Content type	Channels	KPIs	
						Target (month 48)	Status (month 18)
		<p>To trigger applications from Early Career Scientists to the training opportunities</p> <p>To mobilise relevant stakeholder groups to engage with relevant training webinars or workshops</p>	<p>Transnational Access Calls open– apply now!</p> <p>Learn to use the AQUARIUS TA Calls platform!</p> <p>Join our webinar on FAIR data management!</p>	<p>Training material</p> <p>Factsheets</p> <p>Blog</p> <p>Webinars</p> <p>Interviews</p> <p>First Video</p>	<p>Brokerage event</p> <p>Webinars</p> <p>Training events</p> <p>E-mailing lists</p> <p>Events (conferences, workshops, etc)</p>	3+ citizen science groups directly engaged in TNA projects	3+NGOs who engage in citizen science activities engaged in TNA projects
						500+ industry stakeholders targeted	200+ industry stakeholders targeted (email campaign to maritime clusters, LinkedIn)
						+50 applications	19 applications to TA Call 1, 95 applications to training opportunities
						5+ Mission actions informed about AQUARIUS tools and/or services	50+ Mission actions informed (email to CSAs, Poster at Mission Forum, LinkedIn post reposted by Mission LinkedIn account)
						1000 visits to the training repository	172
Uptake (M7-M48)	<p>TG#1</p> <p>TG#2</p> <p>TG#3</p> <p>TG#4</p> <p>TG#5</p>	<p>Disseminate key exploitable results from AQUARIUS to the relevant stakeholder groups</p> <p>Disseminate key exploitable results from the funded</p>	<p>New data flows available – access our AQUARIUS Dataflow Dashboard.</p> <p>Access our training materials – view/download here.</p> <p>Check out our project results</p>	<p>Presentations</p> <p>Posters</p> <p>Social media posts</p> <p>Final video</p> <p>Policy brief</p> <p>Blog</p> <p>Webinars</p>	<p>Website (news, blogs)</p> <p>Meetings & events</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>Open access scientific publications e.g. Zenodo.org</p> <p>EOSC</p> <p>E-mailing lists</p>	+200 Downloads of AQUARIUS outputs	460 downloads of AQUARIUS outputs from Zenodo
						+200 views of AQUARIUS Training Webinars	<p>Webinar TA Call how to apply: 190 views</p> <p>Webinar use TAP: 97 views</p> <p>Webinar Fair data principles: 35 views</p> <p>Webinar data management: 43 views</p> <p>Total: 365 views</p>
						+300 downloads of AQUARIUS policy brief	0

Phase	TG	Objectives	Campaigns	Content type	Channels	KPIs	
						Target (month 48)	Status (month 18)
		projects to relevant stakeholder groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – download/access here Download our AQUARIUS policy brief 		Networks e.g. IOC-IODE	70+ participants informed of AQUARIUS vision and recommendations towards marine and freshwater RIs of the future Further KPI will be developed as part of Task 7.3	0

Table 6. Outreach and engagement campaigns for Call 1

Year	2024					2025
Month	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan
Campaign	Campaign 1: Introducing RI Catalogue	Campaign 2: Introducing Call 1	Campaign 3: Countdown to the call	Campaign 4: Open Call		
Toolkits	AQUARIUS Communication and Outreach Toolkit		AQUARIUS Funding Call 1 Toolkit for partners			
Newsletters/ flashes			AQUARIUS Newsletter 1	Newsflash - AQUARIUS Funding Call 1 now open		
Press release				Press release Issued		
Email campaigns		Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers
Blogs		Blog with focus on AQUARIUS RI Catalogue				
Videos	-	RI Catalogue Blog Video		Promo Video; Insights for applicants blog video		
Website	-	RI Catalogue launched	Website updated with information for Call2	Link to Transnational Access Platform now live		
News (Monthly)	Identifying priorities for Funding Calls; Identifying Data Gaps	First AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	MongGOOS General Assembly; Maximising the value of data collection; Join AQUARIUS Webinar; MARBLUE 2024	First Transnational Access Call Open; Join our AQUARIUS Webinar and learn how to use our TAP; Learn how to submit your proposal in the TAP	Inside the First AQUARIUS Webinar; Link to webinar and training on transnational access platform	First AQUARIUS Regional Lighthouse Access Call is Closed
Webinars	-			AQUARIUS Webinar - Call 1 Announcement and how to apply AQUARIUS Training Webinar		
Social Media W1	Countdown to RI Catalogue launch	Announcing 1st brokerage event at ICES ASM Frank Armstrong blog with focus on RI catalogue	MongGOOS GA: 2nd AQUARIUS Brokerage Event Photos and recap from 2nd AQUARIUS Brokerage event Webinar Announcement: Learn about the Funding Call		Learn how to submit your proposal in the TA Platform FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1 AQUARIUS at HE Impact conf.t	Open funding call! Apply by 20 January
	Call priority report by SYKE	AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	Webinar Announcement: Learn about the Funding Call	AQUARIUS Video:	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	Make sure to register your application early

Social Media W2	Three weeks until the launch of the AQUARIUS RI Catalogue	Join the AQUARIUS Brokerage event		Join the AQUARIUS Webinar Today!	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	
		Photos and Recap: 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event		Webinar recording is now available		
Social Media W3	Data Gaps Report	New article: Summary of 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage event	4 weeks to launch of 1st TA Call + RI catalogue	The 1st AQUARIUS Funding Call is now open! +promo video	TA to RI in all Mission Ocean & Waters Lighthouse Regions	Only 5 days left to apply
	AQUARIUS in Numbers - 2 weeks to go to catalogue launch		SeaTechWeek	Hyperspectral 2024	FAQs about AQUARIUS Call 1	Deadline to apply approaches
			Subscribe to the AQUARIUS Newsletter	AQUARIUS Training Webinar Announcement		The deadline to apply is today
Social Media W4	RV Celtic Explorer feature	New AQUARIUS Gallery	Register to AQUARIUS Webinar on Call 1	Don't miss the AQUARIUS training webinar		
	Meet the AQUARIUS RI providers - 1 week to go until catalogue launch		European Open Science Symposium and AQUARIUS Open Data	Ocean Knowledge Conference 2024		The first AQUARIUS Funding Call is officially closed
Social Media W5	Its Launch Day! AQUARIUS RI Catalogue is live		AQUARIUS 3rd Brokerage Event Announcement: MarBlue Conference	Funding Opportunity for Marine and Freshwater Researchers: AQUARIUS Call 1		
			AQUARIUS Newsletter 1	Insights for applicants		
			Join the AQUARIUS Webinar	Register for Training Webinar		
			-	Euro-Bioimaging Webinar		
Events by AQUARIUS		ICES Science Conference: AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	MonGOOS GA: AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	Tour of SLU's R/V Svea for participants at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	AQUARIUS Brokerage webinar	
			MarBlue: AQUARIUS Brokerage Event	Poster & presentation at Swedish Marine Research Days	AQUARIUS Poster at the BS-SEOS Project meeting	
Events (Third Party)			Presentations at 11th FerryBox Workshop	Euro-Bioimaging Webinar: Info session on 1st AQUARIUS Call	Presentation at the 3as Jornadas Luso Espanolas de Hidrografia (3JLEH)	
			Presentation to ICES EOSG	Hyperspectral 2024	Presentation to French Regional & Offshore scientific commissions	
			Presented to the Explorer Education Program	Presentation at the SLU Aqua research collegium		
			Presentation to the ICES Scallop Assessment Working Group (WGScallop)	Pull-up-banner @ Project Marine Management and Climate (Nordic Council)		

Table 7 Outreach and engagement campaign for Call 2

Year	2025						
Month	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct
Campaign	Campaign 1: Introducing the Call (name, dates, who can apply)		Campaign 3: Countdown to the call			Campaign 4: Open Call	
Toolkits & press releases		Communication Toolkit for pre-launch circulated			Press release + Updated Call 2 Toolkit circulated		
Email campaigns	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers	Emails to networks, personal contacts and multipliers
Newsletters * Newsflash		Newsflash! Call opens Sept, but start preparing now.	Newsletter: CALL 2 Introduction & specificities	Newsflash - Updated Eligibility Criteria		Newsflash on 02 Sept: Call open! Who, what, why, how and when of Call 2	Newsletter Oct 1st: Focus on Call
Blogs		Blog with Carlos Barrera (RI and Training)		Blog with Bernadette Ni Chonghaile (Call 2 updates)		Blog with coordinator to promote TA Call 2	
Videos	Meet the partners - Dre Catrisse	Updated promo video (EMD) - Call 2	Meet the partners - Aodhan Fitzgerald (TA Call 2) Video			How to use the TAP video with Anneli Strobel and Elisabeth de Maio	
Website	Website updates for TA Call 2: new banner; information on call;	Updates to TA Page	Updates on how to apply	Projects funded under TA Call1 (inspiration)			
News (Monthly)	AQUARIUS at EUFAR Webinar; Video-Behind the scenes with of AQUARIUS; Advancing science with citizen science;	AQUARIUS at EGU; AQUARIUS attends EMD; AQUARIUS at OceanICU GA	One Ocean Science Congress; The EU Ocean Pact; AQUARIUS at Oceans 2025; AQUARIUS at ESA Living Planet Symposium; Meet the people behind AQUARIUS	Call for scientific experts - AQUARIUS pool of experts	Get ready for the 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call for Access!	The 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call for Access is now open!; News item: Who, Why, What & How of TA Call 2; Link to TAP goes live	Apply before the deadline+ how to apply
Webinars			WP6 data management webinar available on website	-		AQUARIUS Brokerage Webinar	
Social Media W1	RICH Webinar	AQUARIUS Year 1 Report	Apply for AQUARIUS Seabed Mapping Training programme	AQUARIUS FAIR data management resources		AQUARIUS 2nd Call now open!	Spotlight on air RI

	Blue Cloud Consultation	AQUARIUS EGU	Call 2 is on the Horizon	Important update for AQUARIUS Applicants: Eligibility		TAP video - how to apply	FAQ
	-	-	-		Updated Eligibility Criteria (Targeting Industry)	Spotlight on Mobile Marine Observation Platforms	4 Weeks remaining!
Social Media W2	EUFAR Webinar	Revamped AQUARIUS Video	EU Ocean Pact at UNOC	AQUARIUS RIs for the Mediterranean	AQUARIUS Funded Projects (Inspiration for Call2)	Call 2 Quick Overview Carousel	Register on the TAP as early as possible!
	PLOCAN Summer School Training	ECR - Opportunities - Seabed Mapping	Deadline to apply to PLOCAN Glider School		1 month to go until Call 2 opens!	Who can apply to call 2?	How to apply?
		-	INFOMAR Seabed Mapping Training - Applications Closed			Spotlight on River and Basin Supersites	Sponsored post for Industry and SMEs
Social Media W3	Dre Video	Meet the partners Video	Coordinator Video promoting call 2	Call for experts - AQUARIUS pool of experts	AQUARIUS Funded Projects	Targeted post for Industry and SMEs	Sponsored post for Citizen Science
	EGU	AQUARIUS at EMD	AQUARIUS at Oceans 2025	-	3 Weeks to go until Call 2 Opens!	Targeted post for Citizen Science	2 Weeks to go! Don't wait to the last minute to apply
			-	-	Updated Eligibility Criteria (Targeting Citizen Science)	Targeted post for researchers	FAQ
Social Media W4	Citizen Science Month - Call 2	Get Ready for the 2nd AQUARIUS Funding Call	Countdown to 2nd Funding Call	Bernie Blog - Focus on 2nd Call	AQUARIUS Funded Projects	Spotlight on Fixed Marine Facilities	1 Week to go! How to apply?
		-			2 Weeks to go		
Social Media W5	AQUARIUS at EGU	Presenting TA Call 2 at OceanICU GA	AQUARIUS at ESA Living Planet Symposium 2025	AQUARIUS RIs for the Baltic and North Sea	1 Week to go until Call 2 Opens!	Spotlight on Experimental Research Facilities	The deadline to apply approaches! Dont miss it.
	PLOCAN Summer School Training	-			AQUARIUS Funded Projects	Spotlight on Drones	
	Launching AQUARIUS Call 2 at EGU (3 posts)	-				Spotlight on Satellite Services	
Events by AQUARIUS						Brokerage Webinar	
Events (Third Party)	AQUARIUS Booth at EGU	AQUARIUS at EMD	Poster One Ocean Science Congress	AQUARIUS presented at CS-MACH1 kick-off	EMSEA	All Atlantic Forum 2025	
	RICH Webinar	TA Call2 highlighted at OceanICU GA	Poster Oceans 2025			Poster at the Mission Ocean EU Presidency Conference	
	AQUARIUS at EUFAR Airborne Science Webinar		Presentation at ESA living Planet Symposium			European Research & Innovation Days	

Table 8. AQUARIUS high-level editorial calendar 2025-2026

Year	2025		2026												
Month	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb (M24)	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Jul	Nov	Dec
Phase	All (Awareness, Engagement, Dissemination)		All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All
Project activities and dependencies	Status of TA projects (launch, update, outputs); Possibility of a 3rd Call; Training opportunities and webinars; AQUARIUS outputs/ deliverables; AQUARIUS events & clustering activities; Third-party events		Status of TA projects (launch, update, outputs); Possibility of a 3rd Call; Training opportunities and webinars; AQUARIUS outputs/ deliverables; AQUARIUS events & clustering activities; Third-party events												
Toolkits				Social media kit - General Assembly 3	Social media kit - AQUARIUS Policy Brief										
Newsletters * Newsflash		Quarterly newsletter			Quarterly newsletter			Newsflash (Meet the projects funded under TA Call 2)	Quarterly newsletter			Quarterly newsletter			Quarterly newsletter
Press release					First version of Policy Brief circulated										
Email campaigns															
Blogs	Blog (partner or TA project lead)			Blog (partner or TA project lead)				Blog (partner or TA project lead)			Blog (partner or TA project lead)		Carlos Barrera Blog	Blog (partner or TA project lead)	
Videos			Social media video - meet the partners/projects							Social media video - meet the partners/projects			Updated promo video (EMD)		Social media video - meet the partners/projects
Website	Launch of ADD				brief - first version and external survey (TBC)	details on website, Annual Report available							Update TA Page		
News (Monthly)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)
Webinars	Training webinars TBC with WP5 & 6		Training webinars TBC with WP5 & 6												
Social Media W1	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project
Social Media W2	AQUARIUS @ EU Marine Knowledge week	Read our newsletter	Launch of new training opportunities (2025)	AQUARIUS General Assembly (find out more - sign up to newsletter)	Read our newsletter	Read the Annual Report	AQUARIUS at EMD (find out more, sign up to our newsletter)	Read our newsletter	AQUARIUS Open Science activities	Update on training opportunities	Read our newsletter				Read our newsletter
Social Media W3	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on a RI
Social Media W4 Events by AQUARIUS	Outcome of PLOCAN Glider School			Visit the AQUARIUS DataFlow AQUARIUS General		AQUARIUS Vision for Future R&I - Have your say	AQUARIUS Vision for Future R&I - Have your say	AQUARIUS Vision for Future R&I - Have your say	Promote training opportunities				Introduction Call 2: Eligibility		
Events (Third Party)	EU Marine Knowledge Event (EMODnet Conference, DOF)				EU Ocean Days/ Mission Forum			European Maritime Day							EU Marine Knowledge Event (EMODnet Conference, DOF)

Table 5. AQUARIUS high level editorial calendar 2027-2028

Year	2027												2028		
Month	Jan	Feb (M36)	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb (M48)	
Phase	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	All	
Project activities and dependancies	Status of TA projects (launch, update, outputs); Possibility of a 3rd Call; Training opportunities and webinars; AQUARIUS outputs/ deliverables; AQUARIUS events & clustering activities; Third-party events												Status of TA projects (launch, update, outputs); Possibility of a 3rd Call; Training webinars; AQUARIUS outputs/ deliverables; Clustering Activities; Third party events		
Toolkits		Social media kit - General Assembly 3										launch circulated to partners mid-May		Social media kit - General Assembly 3	
Newsletters * Newsflash Press release			Quarterly newsletter			Quarterly newsletter			Quarterly newsletter			Quarterly newsletter			
Email campaigns															
Blogs		Blog (partner or TA project lead)			Blog (partner or TA project lead)			Blog (partner or TA project lead)			Carlos Barrera Blog	Blog (partner or TA project lead)		Blog (partner or TA project lead)	
Videos	Social media video -meet the partners/riobjects						Social media video -meet the partners/riobjects				Updated promo video (EMD)	Legacy Video ready			
Website				Annual Report Published							Update TA Page		AQUARIUS Policy Brief (Final)	AQUARIUS (final) Annual report	
News (Monthly)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	Monthly news item (Spotlight on TA project)	
Webinars	Training webinars TBC with WP5 & WP6														
Social Media W1	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Spotlight/Update on funded project	Update on funded projects	AQUARIUS Annual Report
Social Media W2	Launch of PLOCAN Glider School Opportunity		Read our newsletter	Annual Report is out	AQUARIUS @ EMD	Read our newsletter			Read our newsletter			AQUARIUS @ Marine Knowledge Days	Read our newsletter	AQUARIUS Policy Brief (Final)	
Social Media W3	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	AQUARIUS at EU ocean Days	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on a RI	Spotlight on RI	Spotlight on a RI	AQUARIUS legacy video	AQUARIUS Comes to an end
Social Media W4 Events by AQUARIUS		AQUARIUS General	Join the Virtual Access and Analytics Training	Virtual Access and Analytics Training Webinar							Introduction Call 2: Eligibility			AQUARIUS Final Event and general Assembly (TBD)	
Events (Third Party)			EU Ocean Days		European Maritime Day							EU Marine Knowledge Event (EMODnet Conference)			

13. Appendix 1

AQUARIUS partners Communication and Dissemination Activity Log (August 2025)

Dissemination activity name*	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity *	Who? Target audience reach *	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
Presentation of AQUARIUS at Blue-Cloud 2026 General Assembly, during session "Synergies & Exploitation"	5/7/2024	Meetings	Research communities	50	Online
Presentation at 'Pint of Science' festival	13-15/05/2024	Other	Citizens	50	Galway, Ireland
Presentation at EMRA'24 (Workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications)	27-29/05/2024	Conferences	Research communities	86	Arenzano, Italy
Proceedings of the 8th IAHR Europe Congress, Lisbon – Portugal, 4-7 June 2024	4-7/06/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Lisbon, Portugal
Poster at International Underwater Glider Conference (IUGC)	10-14, June 2024	Conferences	Research communities		Gothenburg, Sweden
Presentation on AQUARIUS at the 26th European Research Vessel Operators (ERVO) meeting	11-13/06/2024	Conferences	EU institutions		Vigo, Spain
Presentation of AQUARIUS at JERICO-S3 Final General Assembly.	18-21/06/2024	Conferences	Research communities	50-60	Brest, France
EuroGO-SHIP	27/06/2024	Clustering activities	Research communities		
Presentation at International Radiowave Oceanography Workshop (ROW) 2024	3-5/09/2024	Meetings	Research communities	100+	Plymouth, UK
Poster presentation at EU Polar Science Week	3-6/09/2024	Conferences	Research communities	300	Copenhagen, Denmark
AQUARIUS Brokerage event, as side event to the ICES Annual Science Conference	10/9/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Gateshead, United Kingdom
Second AQUARIUS brokerage event, at MonGOOS General Assembly & Workshop	1/10/2024	Meetings	Research communities		Malaga, Spain
Presentation at the 3as Jornadas Luso Espanolas de Hidrografia (3JLEH)	9-11/10/2024	Conferences	Research communities		Cadiz, Spain

Dissemination activity name*	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity *	Who? Target audience reach *	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
Presentation on AQUARIUS at EGI 2024		Conferences	Research communities		Lecce, Italy
Presentations at 11th FerryBox Workshop	1-2/10/2024	Meetings	Other	75	Helsinki, Finland
Presentation to ICES Ecosystem Observation Steering Group (EOSG)	2/10/2024	Meetings	Research communities	29	Online
Presentation to the ICES Scallop Assessment Working Group (WGScallop)	10/10/2024	Meetings	Research communities	44	Online
Presentation at the MarBlue 2024 Conference on MDM in AQUARIUS	24/10/2024	Conferences	Research communities	200	Constanta, Romania
Presented to the Explorer Education Program	10/17/2024	Meetings	Citizens	12	Online
Marblue Conference Observing the Black Sea session Presentation, Poster and exhibition area	23/10/2024	Conferences	Research communities	200	Constanta, Romania
AQUARIUS brokerage webinar	6/11/2024	Other	Other	81	Online
Presentation of AQUARIUS at the SLU Aqua research collegium	7/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	63	Lysekil, Sweden
HYPERSPECTRAL 2024	13-15/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	190	Noordwijk, The Netherlands
<u>Pull-up-banner at the final conference on Project Marine Management and Climate (Nordic Council)</u>	13/11/2024	Conferences	Research communities	150	Göteborg, Sweden
Poster and presentation about AQUARIUS at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	26-28/11/2024	Conference	Research communities	90	Kalmar, Sweden
Tour of SLU's research vessel R/V Svea for participants at the Swedish Marine Research Days 2024	27/11/2024	Other	Research communities	60	Kalmar Sweden
AQUARIUS Training Webinar	27/11/2024	Education and training events	Research communities	12	Online
AQUARIUS Project and Call	02/12/24 & 4/12/24	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities		Online
AQUARIUS Poster at the BS-SEOS Project meeting	17/12/2024	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	Research communities	25	

Dissemination activity name*	Date	Type of Dissemination Activity *	Who? Target audience reach *	Audience Size	Location (city, country)
Presentation of the AQUARIUS to the French Regional & Offshore scientific commissions	04/12/2024 & 06/12/2024	Meetings	Research communities	50	Paris, France
Poster including Aquarius Project at IMDIS Conference (Marine Data and Information Systems)	27-29 May 2024	Conferences	Research communities	50	Bergen, Norway
AQUARIUS poster at VLIZ Marine Science Day	5/3/2025	Conferences	Research communities	300-500	Brugge, Belgium
EGU 2025	27 April - 2 May 2025	Conferences	Research communities		Vienna, Austria
European Maritime Day 2025	21-23 May 2025	Conferences	Other		Cork, Ireland
OceanICU Annual Meeting	23/05/2025	Conferences	Research communities	90	Sopot, Poland
Presented 'Spaceborne, airborne and drone-based water quality monitoring' and AQUARIUS TA call 2 at EUFAR Webinar: 25 years of airborne research in Europe	6/4/2025	Meetings	Research communities	40	Online
Demo, to present AQUARIUS Funding Call for Access and Remote Sensing Infrastructure offered by VITO, presented at VITO booth at the ESA Living Planet Symposium	24/06/2025	Conferences	Research communities	10000	Vienna, Austria
Online poster Oceans Conference Brest		Conferences	Research communities	500	
AQUARIUS-EMSO poster focused on access to deep-sea infrastructures		Conferences		800	France
Promotion of TA call 2 at Ocean ICU General Assembly		Project General Assembly			Sopot, Poland
Oceans Conference Brest					Brest, France

14. Appendix 2

Table 6. Hashtag library

Aquatic Ecosystems	Followers	Research & data	Followers	Environment	Followers
#Water	45044	#DATA	6097370	#ClimateChange	165550
#Marine	39992	#Research	631131	#Sustainable	57517
#Biodiversity	34431	#Collaboration	401905	#Conservation	33660
#Nature	24964	#Community	136377	#Chemical	31556
#Ecosystem	6781	#Science	128286	#Protection	21030
#Ocean	5832	#OpenSource	47637	#Plastic	14485
#Ecosystems	2544	#DataManagement	30913	#ClimateCrisis	13876
#Delta	1700	#Connect	29693	#WaterQuality	9616
#Algae	1369	#Knowledge	15311	#NorthSea	7707
#OceanConservation	1227	#Integration	10582	#CarbonNeutral	6909
#habitat	1193	#Volunteer	9463	#NatureBasedSolutions	6284
#Interface	936	#Satellite	7489	#PFAS	5872
#River	623	#Monitoring	6619	#Pollution	5632
#Coastal	579	#OpenData	5920	#PlasticPollution	4349
#Freshwater	474	#Interoperability	5395	#MarineConservation	1634
#Coast	195	#Networks	4823	#Habitat	1198
#Aquatic	160	#Connecting	4714	#Arctic	1079
#CoastalManagement	135	#Cooperation	4594	#NaturalCapital	983
#MarineBiodiversity	105	#MarineBiology	3837	#MarineScience	901
#Basin	76	#EarthObservation	3297	#EcosystemServices	866
#Shoreline	74	#Modelling	2130	#NBS	618
#MarineEcosystems	42	#OpenScience	1951	#Species	323
#Estuary	13	#Oceanography	1178	#Atlantic	323
#CoastalScience	9	#CitizenScience	1029	#Prevent	314
#LandSea	6	#Observation	486	#Danube	290
#CoastalEcology	3	#CoDesign	414	#NatureRestoration	241
#CoastalDevelopment	3	#PublicEngagement	403	#BalticSea	240

Policy	Followers	RIs	Followers	Funding Calls	Followers	Audiences	Followers
#DATA	6097370	#Infrastructure	116538	#Careers	22241681	#Industry	17871
#Strategy	5026845	#Aircraft	47136	#Internship	482497	#PostDoc	16517
#DigitalTwin	13641	#DataCenter	28584	#Opportunity	295173	#Academia	13473
#EU	12072	#Drones	16431	#Internship	122491	#Researchers	9884
#OneHealth	8824	#Facilities	16085	#Apply	73623	#SME	7106
#EUGreenDeal	6842	#Vessel	15483	#ApplyNow	69529	#Scientists	4650
#HorizonEU	3288	#Drone	14002	#Funding	61161	#PhDStudents	1348
#BlueEconomy	3145	#DataCentre	5921	#CareerGrowth	23467	#EarlyCareer	1347
#EUFunding	490	#Catalogue	767	#Grants	3979	#CitizenScience	1054
#SciencePolicy	396	#RV	537	#FundingOpportunities	867	#Policymakers	837
#EUCommission	322	#Aircrafts	427	#ResearchFunding	766	#Citizens	626
#OceanLiteracy	258	#DataInfrastructure	421	#EUFunding	492	#DecisionMakers	442
#EUProject	170	#Experimental	228	#Calls	228	#CoastalCommunities	93
#REA	152	#Fixed	182	#GetFunded	191	#Fishers	67
#MissionOcean	137	#VirtualLab	65	#TrainingOpportunity	141	#Oceanographers	9
#EURResearch	105	#ResearchVessel	59	#TransnationalAccess	7	#EUCitizens	8
#UNOceanDecade	43	#ResearchInfrastructure	45	#GetFunding	2	#Hydrographers	5
#EUMission	26	#ExperimentalResearch	24	#FloatingUniversity	2	#MarineScientists	2
#DigitalTwinOcean	10	#SatelliteServices	16	#fundingCalls	0		
#LandSeaLot	2	#Supersite	2				
#MappingtheOcean	2	#MarineFacilities	1				
#EUDTO	2	#MobileMarineObservationPlatform	0				
#MissionLighthouse	0	#MarineObservationPlatform	0				

15. Appendix 3

Table 7. Partner LinkedIn and Twitter handles

Partner	LinkedIn handle	X handle
The Marine Institute	Marine Institute	@MarineInst
Finnish Meteorological Institute	Finnish Meteorological Institute	@meteorologit
The Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	CSIC	@CSIC
Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	@HcmrInOcean
Norwegian Institute of Marine Research (IMR)	Institute of Marine Research (IMR), Norway	NA
Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR)	Grønlands Naturinstitut	NA
Seascope Belgium (SSBE)	Seascope Belgium	@SeascopeBelgium
Centre for Materials and Coastal Research GmbH (HEREON)	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	@HereonHelmholtz
Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)	Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	@AWI_Media
University of Limerick (UL)	University of Limerick (UL)	@UL
National Research and Development Institute Marina Grigore Antipa (INCDM)	National Institute for Marine Research and Development "Grigore Antipa"	NA
Mariene Informatie Service, (MARIS)	MARIS B.V.	NA
The Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE)	Finnish Environment Institute (Syke) - Suomen ympäristökeskus (Syke)	@SYKEint
National Research Council, Italy (CNR)	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	@CNRsocial_
CzechGlobe	CzechGlobe	@czechglobe_offi
Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)	Norsk institutt for vannforskning (NIVA)	@NIVAforskning
Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS)	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences	NA
Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)	VLIZ - Flanders Marine Institute	@VLIZnews
European Marine Biological Resource Centre European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMBRC-ERIC)	EMBRC - European Marine Biological Resource Centre	@EMBRC_EU
Sorbonne University (SU) EMBRC-FR	EMBRC France	@EmbrcFrance
Algarve Centre of Marine Sciences	Universidade do Algarve	@UALg
Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research CIIMAR	CIIMAR	@CiimarUp
Mercator Ocean (MOi)	Mercator Ocean International	@MercatorOcean
European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)	EMBL	@embl
The Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)	SMHI	@SMHI
The Research Institute for Development, France (IRD)	IRD	NA
University of Liège (ULIEGE)	University of Liège	@UniversiteLiege

Partner	LinkedIn handle	X handle
National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, Italy (INGV)	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia	@INGV_press
Hydrographic Institute, Portugal	Instituto Hidrográfico - Marinha Portuguesa	NA
Norve Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE)	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre	@NORCEresearch
Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands (PLOCAN)	Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN)	@plocan
The Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System (SOCIB)	NA	@socib_icts
The Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO)	VITO	@VITObelgium
European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EMSO ERIC)	EMSO ERIC	@EMSOeu
The National Research-Development Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology (GeoEcoMar)	GeoEcoMar	@GeoEcoMar
Havstovan Faroe Marine Research Institute (HAV)	NA	NA
Interact-International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring (INTERACT)	INTERACT	@INTERACT66
INKODE Cooperative Society (INKODE)	INKODE soc. coop.	NA
National Institute of Oceanography and Experimental Geophysics, Italy (OGS)	OGS	@OGS_IT
French Research Institute for the Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER)	Ifremer	@Ifremer_fr
Marine And Freshwater Research Institute (MFRI)	NA	NA
Technical University of Catalonia	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	@la_UPC
Stichting Nederlandse Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek Instituten [Foundation for Dutch Scientific Research Institutes] (NWO-I)	NWO-I	@NWO_Nieuws
Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TUBITAK)	TÜBİTAK	@Tubitak
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)	SLU - Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	@_SLU